

Change Management and Introduction Processes of the Digital Solutions used for assisting Elderly People with Cognitive Impairment <WP2 Y1Q3>

Task leader: Fondazione Politecnico di Milano

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Executive Summary

Change Management practices will form a strong pillar of the four DECI Pilot Sites, by supporting the introduction of ICT-enabled functionalities within the four healthcare environments through a set of guidelines and indications for the fruitful management of the transition from the *as is* to the desired *to be* state.

Therefore, Change Management guidelines detailed in this document will directly support design of Pilot Sites as part of Work Package 5 activities. Moreover, this document will focus on the detailing of a set of indications and suggestions for the management of Pilot Sites change, which will have a direct impact on the success of Pilot Projects themselves.

Starting from a structured literature analysis and an investigation of running and recent Change Management initiatives within healthcare environments, Section 2 of this document aims at detailing a set of inputs and indications for the fruitful management of change as part of the DECI Pilot Projects. The main elements emerging from Lewin's and Kotter's widespread models to manage and lead change are used as a starting point for the identification of guidelines that can be applied to innovation within healthcare process and, most notably, improvement of elderly people management initiatives.

Building on these analyses of relevant literature and healthcare-based case studies, a complementary evaluation of cultural characteristics of the four Pilot Sites countries is carried out in Section 3, starting from Hofstede's and Ferraro's models and identifying behavioural elements that can turn out to be impactful within the Pilot Projects. This literature analysis has been complemented with case-by-case evaluations of local characteristics, focusing on the detailing of relevant cultural features to evaluate as part of or in accordance with Change Management guidelines.

Merging the literature-based and the cultural-focused perspectives, Section 4 of this Deliverable provides indications to support DECI Pilot Project designs, detailing general-level, healthcare-specific and country-specific inputs for Change Management.

Closing considerations focus on the potential measurements of change to perform within Project monitoring activities, therefore linking to Project Work Package 6 – which focuses on the evaluation of business, industrial and quality impacts of the Project – and Deliverable 1.5 – dealing with the design of the Pilots based on the pre-Pilot studies. Section 5 recaps a list of potential parameters to monitor for the evaluation of change, to tackle in conjunction with other technology-focused and process-related KPIs.

1 Introduction

This Deliverable is the output of Task 2.3: “Change Management and introduction processes of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with Cognitive Impairment”.

The goal of this document is to present a set of inputs and guidelines for the definition of Pilot Site-specific change actions as part of Pilot Projects implementation, which will be performed as part of Project Work Package 5. These inputs were gathered from various literature sources, both with a general and non-environment-specific perspective and with a healthcare-focused viewpoint, so as to ensure a fruitful evaluation of practices for the management of change.

These were rationalized in accordance with a widespread Change Management model and detailed according to DECI’s characteristics. To further improve the analyses and tackle the perspective of regional characteristics, the evaluation of cultural settings and features was performed, so as to accompany a literature-generated analysis with a DECI-specific evaluation of priorities and local boundaries.

The result is a set of indications and suggestions to support the detailing of Pilot Projects’ actions, with an eye for the fruitful implementation of change in terms of spreading of a vision and culture of change, removal of barriers and sustainment of change momentum.

2 Key Change Management Practices and Trends

This Section details the results of the Change Management literature analysis, highlighting relevant literature practices and trends.

The first subsection presents a brief overview of the analyzed literature, which is then examined in depth and discussed in subsection 2.2.

The goal of Section 2 of this document is therefore to present a comprehensive overview of:

1. Main strategies and approaches used to introduce digital solutions into real settings;
2. Actors and competences that are necessary to efficiently and effectively introduce the digital solutions;
3. Main barriers to overcome during Change Management processes and practices to overcome emerging issues during Change Management projects;
4. Communication activities through which the benefits associated to the usage of digital solutions is presented to their stakeholders.

These analyses will form the preliminary baseline for the declination of Change Management inputs within the DECI Project, as presented in Section 4.

2.1 Overview of analyzed Change Management Literature

Main literature analysis focused, in its first step, on well-established theoretical Change Management models and methodologies, highlighting best practices and consolidated approaches for the management of change within innovation projects.

After this preliminary analysis, a more refined study was carried out, expanding on the topic by researching relevant articles and essays on the theme, with the goal of both upholding theoretical literature findings and present different perspectives on the topic.

Finally, a third, more context-specific analysis was performed, with the goal of evaluating Change Management practices within environments bearing similarities with the DECI Project.

To simplify literature overview, this analysis can be schematized into a three-tier structure:

1. Tier one: theoretical literature on Change Management;
2. Tier two: non-context-specific literature elaborating on Change Management practices, expanding and commenting on traditional models;
3. Tier three: context-specific literature elaborating on Change Management practices within a healthcare-related environment.

The following table presents a brief summary of the analyzed literature. More information on the analyzed articles and essays can be found in Section 7.

Tier	Author	Title	Year
1	Deming, W.E.	<i>The New Economics: for Industry, Government, Education</i>	2000
1	Kotter, J.P.	<i>Leading Change</i>	1996
1	Kotter, J.P.	<i>The Heart of Change</i>	2002
1	Kotter, J.P.	<i>Accelerate!</i>	2012
1	Kotter, J.P.	<i>Accelerate: Building Strategic Agility for Faster-Moving World</i>	2014
1	Ishikawa, K.	<i>What is Total Quality Control? The Japanese Way</i>	1985
1	Morrison, M.	<i>Organizational Development Theory and Practice</i>	2014
1	Shewhart, W.A.	<i>Economic Control of Quality of Manufactured Product</i>	1980
2	Bartezzaghi, E.	<i>L'Organizzazione dell'Impresa: Processi, progetti, Conoscenza, Persone</i>	2010

2	Irish Health Service Executive (HSE)	<i>Improving Our Services: a User's Guide to Managing Change in the Service Executive</i>	2008
2	Langley, G.J.	<i>The Improvement Guide: a practical Approach to Enhancing Organizational performance</i>	2009
3	Auguste, J.	<i>Applying Kotter's 8-Step Process for Leading Change to the Digital Transformation of an Orthopaedic Surgical Practice Group in Toronto, Canada</i>	2013
3	Bartholomew, J., Moore, B.	<i>A guide to Becoming a Dementia-Friendly Community</i>	2014
3	Campbell, R.J.	<i>Change Management in Healthcare</i>	2008
3	U.S. Department of Health and Human Services – National Learning Consortium	<i>Change Management in HER Implementation</i>	2013
3	Johnson, S., Ostaszkiwicz, J., O'Connell, B.	<i>Moving beyond Resistance to Restrain Minimization: a Case Study of Change Management in Aged Care</i>	2009

Table 1 – Clustered literature overview

2.2 Change Management Practices for the Implementation of Digital Solutions

This Section presents and discusses the main results of the performed Change Management literature analysis. The topics are organized in four main sub-sections, elaborating on the three-tier structure presented in the previous Section:

1. Theoretical literature is the core topic of Section 2.2.1, where Lewin's and Kotter's models are introduced, to define a set of general guidelines for the management of change; because the two models bear similarities in their general structure, this Section is organized in accordance with Lewin's three main steps, tracing affinities with Kotter's steps;
2. Thanks to its high level of detail and applicability to different contexts, in Section 2.2.2, Kotter's model is used as a general outline to evaluate Change Management practices with an eye for the healthcare processes;
3. Section 2.2.3 presents a different approach to Change Management, tackling the more recent trend of perceiving change as a cyclic process and introducing the Continuous Improvement methodology (Deming, 2000);
4. Finally, Section 2.2.4 wraps up the discussion and gathers relevant evidences emerged from the overall literature analysis.

Throughout the sections, various actors' perspectives are taken into consideration: technological partners, hospitals and care providers, patients, policy makers, etc. As

Change Management issues affect various actors involved in an innovation initiative, key aspects to take into consideration are examined all throughout the sub-sections.

2.2.1 Lewin’s Three-Step Model to manage Change and its similarities with Kotter’s Model for Leading Change

Two of the most important Change Management models emerging from literature have been conceived and defined in the form of a multiple-step process to support and lead change.

Kurt Lewin’s model, designed in the 1950s, is a three-stage model conceived to guide and support change and is commonly referred to as an *unfreeze, change, freeze* model, from the name of its three main steps (for more information, see Morrison, 2014).

The model presents a general structure of steps and related practices meant to create a favourable environment for the execution of change, as detailed in the following picture.

Figure 1 - Lewin’s Three-Step Model to Manage Change¹

Kotter’s eight-step model, designed in 1996 and updated throughout the 2000s and the 2010s, is focused on practices for the effective leading of change and lays its foundation in the identification of the opportunity of change (for a detailed presentation of the model, see Kotter & Cohen 2002). Its eight steps are detailed in the following figure.

¹ Lewin, K., 1951, *Field Theory in Social Science*, New York, Harper and Row

Figure 2 - Kotter's Eight-Step Model for Leading Change²

Possessing a more detailed structure than Lewin's, Kotter's model bears similarities with the former. Therefore, the following sub-sections present a general set of Change Management guidelines following Lewin's model, while tracing their similarities with Kotter's scheme, which is discussed in the details in Section 2.2.2.

This link between Lewin's and Kotter's model are exemplified in the following picture and expanded in the following sub-sections.

Figure 3 - The link between Lewin's and Kotter's model²

² Kotter, J.P., 1996. *Leading Change*, Boston: Harvard Business School Press.

2.2.1.1 Unfreeze

This step deals with the preparation for the actual change. It consists in the understanding of the necessity for change and the comprehension that all involved stakeholders have to be willing to move from the current comfort zone. In order to prepare for change the pros of the change have to be weighed against its cons, to validate the need for change (Morrison, 2014).

The Unfreezing process in the Lewin's model bears similarities with the following first three steps of the Kotter's model:

1. **Create a sense of urgency:** unfreeze the organization by creating a compelling reason for why change is needed; craft and use a significant opportunity as a means for exciting people to sign up to change their organization;
2. **Build a guiding coalition:** creating a cross-functional, cross-level group of people with enough power to lead change; assemble a group with the power and energy to lead and support a collaborative change effort;
3. **Form a strategic vision and initiative:** create a vision and a strategic plan to guide the change process, shape the vision to help steer the change effort and develop strategic initiatives to achieve that vision.

The goal of this entire step is to overcome preliminary barriers that could impair the execution of change. All stakeholders affected by the effects of change should be involved in this activity, with a specific focus on the guiding coalition, responsible for the leading of change.

2.2.1.2 Change

Once the unfreeze stage is done the change process can start. Change is here tackled as a process, or a transition, in the form of an inner movement or journey performed in reaction to a perceived and shared need. This process gravitates around stakeholders assuming new roles, tasks and responsibilities: therefore, more time can be required to participate and react proactively to change.

According to Lewin's model, all major changes in the organization take place within this step (Morrison, 2014). Therefore, a direct comparison can be traced in Kotter's steps 4, 5 and 6, as they directly deal with the performing, leading and management of change:

1. **Enlist a volunteer army:** create and implement a communication strategy that consistently communicates the new vision and strategic plan; raise a large force of people who are ready, willing and urgent to drive change;
2. **Enable action by removing barriers:** remove obstacles to change, alter systems or structures that pose threats to the achievement of the vision; if needed, transform organizational boundaries and encourage risk-taking approaches;
3. **Generate short-term wins:** plan and create short-term wins or improvements, recognizing and rewarding people who contribute to these wins; consistently

produce, track, evaluate and celebrate volumes of small/large accomplishments – correlate to results, to motivate all involved stakeholders.

The stage is often the hardest as change participants are unsure or even fearful: support is important and can happen in the form of training and coaching. Expecting mistakes should be a cornerstone for the process, while simultaneously promoting role models and allowing people to develop their own solutions for the implementation of change.

It is also useful to keep iterating a clear picture of the desired change and the benefits to people, so all stakeholders can keep sight on the overall goal.

2.2.1.3 Freezing or re-freezing

To ensure that the changes applied in the previous steps are systematized, further actions are required (Morrison, 2014). As the name suggests, this stage is focused on establishing stability once change has been put into practice. The overall goal of this step is to make sure changes are accepted and become the new norm. People are required to form new relations and become comfortable with their routines.

The corresponding steps in the Kotter's model deal with how the freezing process can be managed. As per Lewin's model, activities focus on the aftermath on change and the performing of follow-up activities, meant to institute and consolidate change. These include:

1. **Sustain acceleration:** use increasing credibility to change systems, structures and policies that don't align with the vision; hire, promote and develop employees who can implement the vision; reinvigorate the acceleration with new projects and themes;
2. **Institute change:** reinforce the changes by highlighting and articulating connections between new behaviours, process and organizational success; develop means to ensure leadership development and succession.

The freezing step can be one of the most time-consuming phases of the whole process, as the outcomes of change can require time to be fully incorporated and accepted. All stakeholders are once again involved, with the goal to overcome still-persisting barriers and work towards the consolidation of change within the organization.

As change is typically considered part of a cyclic process, Kotter insists on the importance of viewing the institution of change as a preparatory activity for future changes, including the preparation of a leadership succession.

2.2.2 Kotter's Eight-Step Model for Leading Change and its Declination in Healthcare

This Section details – and is structured in accordance to – the eight steps of Kotter's model for leading change, presenting relevant evidences on Change Management issues gathered from literature and focusing on real experiences, with an eye for healthcare-

based initiatives and elderly-care-related projects. These examples of real cases and the healthcare-centred literature focused on healthcare are highlighted in dedicated boxes.

2.2.2.1 Create a Sense of Urgency

According to Kotter's model, the first step to manage any change process is to make sure that sufficient people act with sufficient urgency. There are four types of behaviours that hinder the launch of the required change (Kotter & Cohen 2002):

1. Complacency, driven by false pride or arrogance;
2. Immobilization, self protection due to fear;
3. *You-can't-make-me-move* deviance, driven by ire;
4. Pessimism and hesitation.

Various measures should be undertaken to deal with these behaviours. A sense of urgency should be created in the organization, motivating people to act immediately. This can be done using the *See-Feel-Change* approach (Kotter & Cohen 2002). Authors suggest:

1. Showing what are the main problems to be solved, how they can be solved and why the change is needed.
2. Finding a similar reality that has successfully adopted a similar solution; stakeholders should appreciate the possibility of:
 - a. Observing the solution in a real setting;
 - b. Understanding which benefits could be reached if adopted in their context;
 - c. Ask questions and discuss with the people that are already using that solution.
3. Creating a *mini-crisis* in order to force people to move out of their comfort zone: this way of proceeding could be extremely fast in achieving the result; nevertheless it is also extremely risky because it could generate panic that could block further attempts to change;
4. Bringing in people who already have a sense of urgency (e.g. regarding the state of health care for the elderly people).

Auguste (2013) applied Kotter's eight-steps model to the digital transformation of an orthopaedic surgical practice group in Toronto. The initiative mostly dealt with the introduction of an Electronic Medical Record (EMR) solution coherent with the OntarioMD program. The creation of the sense of urgency was inducted stressing the deadlines related to funding imposed by Ontario MD.

In tackling the creation of a sense of urgency it is important to assess the initial degree of urgency in the organization. Literature suggests that the key questions to ask to determine this degree are the following (HSE 2008):

1. *What is the degree of urgency of the change?*

2. *What are the operational and people implications of this degree of urgency?*
3. *What are the implications in terms of readiness, moral and stamina?*

After these questions are asked, it is then important to create a plan through which the sense of urgency has to be propagated within the organization.

The National Learning Consortium (2013), through the experience about the implementation of EHR in U.S., offers some examples and suggestions about the various step of Kotter's model. Regarding this step, it recommends to: (i) clarify what would happen if the change did not take place; (ii) specify the need to carry out all the related activities as soon as possible.

Bartholomew et al. (2014) analyze the development process of a "dementia-friendly" community and provide some suggestions about the various activities that it is possible to perform during Kotter's eight-step model. Regarding the first step, authors recommend to: (i) obtain statistics on dementia for the specific area/region and identify the trends (e.g. increase in percentage of people with dementia); (ii) activate dialogues, involving local politicians, community leaders, patients with dementia, their families and care givers; (iii) create a story about daily issues faced by patient with dementia and their families.

2.2.2.2 Build a Guiding Coalition

After the first step, the feeling of urgency helps putting together the right group of stakeholders to drive change activities. A powerful and effective guiding group should possess two characteristics: it should be composed of the *right* people and it should be based on team working as its main pillar (Kotter 1996).

According to Campbell (2008) – who focused his attention on Change Management practices in the healthcare sector – the candidates for the guiding team should possess knowledge and competence on: (i) the changes occurring and characterizing the healthcare sector; (ii) the benefits related to the solution to be implemented.

Furthermore, they should be credible with peers and know the inner workings dynamics of the group or division in which they operate. Moreover, they should possess leadership skills allowing them to convey a vision and to motivate colleagues. Finally, they should be able to plan, organize and control activities.

Apart from putting together the right team of individuals, other issues to take into consideration once the guiding team has been formed include ensuring trust among the

members of the team, in order to avoid lack of transparency between the members of the group. The group meetings often lead to frustrations and fights between participants. It is therefore very important to plan and manage guided meetings to minimize frustration and increase trust (Kotter & Cohen, 2002).

As Campbell (2008) suggests, the team should consist of subjects possessing a formal authority within the targeted ecosystem. The author provides an example about two different guiding teams, instituted as part of an initiative focused on the implementation of a computerized physician order entry system.

The first “Design Team”, composed by a laboratory technician, a pharmacist, a radiology technician, information systems personnel, nurses, and clinical staff.

The second “Physician Consultant Team”, was composed of junior and senior physicians from all the various departments (e.g. oncology, gynaecology, cardiology, etc.), playing the role of approving the design and operational policies developed by the first team.

Both teams, while operating in parallel, validated design elements, policies, implementation steps and training methodologies related the project. By limiting interactions between the two teams, both were able to freely express preferences and perspectives, with little to no interference among them, despite the implicit hierarchies that might persist between the two teams.

Auguste (2013) provides a further example about the creation of a guiding team through the involvement of an administrative champion and a physician champion. The two played the role of educators and motivators all the employees involved in the innovation project, providing feedbacks and helping communicate the vision to all involved subjects.

Aside from a set of relevant individuals within the initiative, the extended involvement of all interested stakeholders within an innovation process can play a crucial role for the cross-organizational promotion of an effective discussion on the topic, therefore ensuring that *Guiding Coalition* builds a sustainable solution for all the foreseeable innovation problems (Kotter & Cohen 2002).

On this topic, the National Learning Consortium (2013), recommends to: (i) identify a champion or various champions – both from the administrative and clinical staff – that conduct the guiding team; (ii) engage staff in the whole activity with participative actions.

Bartholomew et al. (2014), regarding this step as part of the creation of a “dementia-friendly” community, recommend to: (i) identify some people that can be leaders; (ii) arrange a meeting to talk about the solution that will be developed; (iii) identify reasons of change; (iv) use medias to support the construction of the guiding team.

Johnson et al. (2009) describe the development, implementation and evaluation of a restraint minimization program for “older people with dementia in a residential aged care setting”. Regarding the second step of Kotter’s model, authors describe the creation of a “project team” and, in parallel to that, of a multidisciplinary team composed of experts “from medicine, nursing, allied health, and therapy” and with the goal of supporting Change Management activities, by minimizing adoption barriers by getting involved in all the project activities.

2.2.2.3 Form a strategic Vision and Initiative

After the definition of a guiding team, this *coalition* should focus on the change vision and, according to Kotter and Cohen (2002), answer the following questions to effectively manage the change:

1. What change is needed and what should not be altered in the targeted environment?
2. What is the best way to turn the vision into a consolidated reality?
3. What change strategies can be considered as unacceptably dangerous?

The general characteristics that a vision statement should possess are clarity and brevity of articulation (Kotter & Cohen 2002).

As a general note for the fruitful development of a vision statement, Kotter recommends the identification of a panel of up to six/seven individual vision perspectives for the future – identifying key dimensions that would help describing the available options for each vision.

*An example of individual visions perspectives in socio-care is provided by Campbell, (2008): (i) what **Support staff** would be needed to sustain this vision? (ii) how would the vision affect **health care professionals** and medical staff? (iii) how would this vision affect **patients**? (iv) under this vision, what kind of **care activity** could be provided to patients? (v) what are the major **competitors**, what actions are they performing in the area and can the vision sustain this competition? (vi) what **action steps** must be taken to make this option attainable?*

After the definition of the diffusion of the vision, the guiding team should devise a strategy to achieve it, by developing plans to implement the strategy and work towards the acquisition and management of required funds (Kotter & Cohen 2002).

On the topic and coherently with Kotter's suggestions, Bartholomew (2014) recommends to: (i) define values that will support all the required changes and verify that all the members of the guiding team can follow these values; (ii) define a work plan in order to allow people to recognize project steps that are coherent with the vision and identify roles and responsibilities within the change project; (iii) specify the expected results and a realistic goal balancing between what is feasible and what is desirable.

The National Learning Consortium (2013) insists on the importance of a clear definition of the desired to be state and recommends to: (i) create a vision through the design of a future state that should include priorities and goals; (ii) establish a well defined project plan to share among all participants.

2.2.2.4 Enlist a Volunteer Army

The goal of this stage is to enlist as many people as possible, acting in unison to translate the shared vision into a reality. The vision statement drafted in the previous step has to be widely communicated – preferably using real examples in order to ensure credibility and ease to understand (Kotter & Cohen 2002).

The authors also suggest that another key aspect for spreading the vision is related to the choice of the communication channels. The general guidelines that should be kept in mind are:

1. Keeping communication simple and heartfelt, not complex and technocratic;
2. *Doing your homework* before communicating, especially to understand what people are *feeling*;
3. Speaking to people's anxieties, confusion, anger and distrust;
4. Ridding communication channels of junk so that important messages can go through;
5. Using new technologies to help people see the vision.

Kotter suggests that whenever a change is about to take place, involved subjects begin to wonder how this could affect them on a personal level. To quell negative feelings, the guiding coalition must develop methods of communication addressing these issues and helping employees to think and behave in accordance with the new direction of change.

Over the course of a change project, different individuals and groups will have different perceptions towards the happening change. The guiding team can use generated

projections to tailor specific messages towards individuals or groups, to help them overcome the perceived issues and recognize the value of change.

To strategically plan for a successful buy-in, a guiding team can adopt the layered approach depicted in the following figure (Campbell 2008), which is based on three aspects:

1. **Communicating the vision**, through the development of an engaging story, which catches the attention of the initiated change process;
2. **Engaging in a continuous dialogue**, through the organization of a question-and-answer (Q&A) session;
3. **Enrolling the organization in the change effort**, by increasing the commitment of individuals and groups regarding the change project; new technologies can be a useful resource to engage subjects in the change process: Kotter (2012) offers an example of an online portal providing information to employees about their jobs in order to understand the relevance of the required change.

Figure 4 - Communicate for Buy-In Layered Model³

³ Campbell, R.J., 2008. *Change Management in Health Care*. The Health Care Manager, 27(1), pp.23–39.

Figure 1 –

Campbell (2008) exemplifies how Ohio State University Health system (OSUHS) communicated for buy-in across all levels of its organization, in accordance with the previous figure. OSUHS developed a physician consultant team charged with designing every order pathway from basic consult to laboratories for their Computerized Physician Order Entry (CPOE) system. The group met to discuss prototypes of order pathways and, after each discussion, the physicians asked their colleagues to comment on the prototype. Then, they shared the observations with the consultant team and system programmers. This cycle was followed until the selected pathway was completed.

Auguste (2013) highlights how, within an healthcare environment, the adoption of multiple parallel channels proved to be very effective. These included: (i) e-mail reminders; (ii) the scheduling and performing of individual interviews; (iii) face-to-face meetings; (iv) “electronic feedbacks from the EMR program”.

This multi-channel approach is confirmed by Bartholomew et al. (2014), who, regarding this step as part of the creation of a “dementia-friendly” community, recommend to: (i) adopt medias and various communication channels to share the vision and the undertaken activities; (ii) choose people with dementia and high profile people as spokesmen; (iii) use stories to increase the sense of urgency; (iv) be sure that the members of the guiding team communicate, possibly with enthusiasm, with the people of their organizations and groups providing them examples regarding the undertaken activities.

2.2.2.5 Enable Action by removing Barriers

The fifth step of Kotter’s model focuses on the empowerment of individual and enabling of direct actions, through the removal of barriers (Kotter & Cohen 2002). According to the authors, there are four different kinds of barriers, which prevent change in an organization:

1. Boss barriers, when the manager does not agree with the vision;
2. System barriers, when the bureaucracy within the organization could obstacle change;
3. Barriers in people’s mind, when employees do not possess enough confidence to face change;
4. Information barriers, when a lack of information or power is perceived throughout the organization.

According to Campbell (2008) there are various alternative ways to overcome these barriers within the healthcare context.

Boss barriers are usually due to a staff member refusing the adoption of change within the process. The author suggests the use of a direct approach, aiming to share change's value with the resisting "boss": through a "see-feel-change" method, authors consider possible to affect behaviours. Instead of communicating numbers, data and facts about the advantages of the solution, the "boss" should directly experience how change is expected to improve present conditions.

System barriers could be overcome through incentives and promotions for the people who follow, support and drive the change. The author considers a reward-based system as very effective.

Barriers related to people's mind could be contained through the support of people who already faced a similar change. These subjects can be seen as consultants, comforting employees and proving experiences on the advantages of change.

The problem of lack of information should be handled and resolved providing feedbacks to employees about their performances.

As part of the development of a "dementia-friendly" community, Bartholomew et al. (2014), recommend to: (i) bring in the guiding team to detect and classify all the potential barriers in term of expected risks; (ii) bring in the guiding team to reduce or remove all perceived barriers through dedicated strategies and actions; (iii) provide incentives for the personnel who ensures that change takes place and publicly reward them; (iv) seek the support of agencies, foundations, businesses, trusts, who could support the removal of barriers.

With an eye for elderly care-related projects, Johnson et al. (2009) list the that should be carried out in this phase: (i) offering experiential exercise, where nursing staff members undergo activities designed to understand the need for change through the perception of patients; (ii) offering the opportunity to visit a facility that has already implemented a similar project; (iii) organizing meetings with staff members and management to discuss benefits and threats of change.

Authors also suggests to provide education programs addressing the needs of specific patients, to better evaluate the needs of all subjects involved in the change process.

2.2.2.6 Generate Short-Term Wins

Authors (Kotter & Cohen 2002) suggest that faith in change should be nurtured, promoting quick wins to support commitment towards change. Through tangible and perceivable wins, it is recommended to motivate employees that directly affect the outcome of change, reinforcing their faith in change and *building momentum*.

Furthermore, it is valuable to engage other employees whose contribution can prove useful in terms of power and role inside the organization, to further support people managing the Change Management project. Short-term wins are vital because they provide: (i) feedbacks for change leaders on their strategy and vision; (ii) sources of motivation for those carrying out change; (iii) *bait*s for those who are not supporting the change process, as quick wins contribute to the diffusion of faith in change; (iv) ways to weaken cynics.

Campbell (2008) provides an example on the usefulness of quick wins within Change Management Projects in healthcare. One of the first actions performed as part of a large-scale reengineering project was the installation of a computerized physician order entry system and the institution of a team of physicians acting as consultants.

These physicians created structured pathways for the introduction of this system, granting that the implementation of each project step is effectively communicated to the rest of the organization and presented in the form of individual achievements for the improvement of the existing care process. With this, other employees could perceive how the change process was moving forward, providing good results.

Auguste (2013) highlights how the quick wins in the introduction of an EMR solution were obtained through structured reviews and approval of the implemented EMR solution elements. These activities took place as part of meetings with the instituted “physician champion” and a representative of the EMR program who provided project funding.

Bartholomew et al. (2014) confirmed the theoretical suggestions of Kotter and Cohen, and, within a “dementia-friendly” community project, recommend to: (i) foresee and perform activities that are feasible and short-term oriented within the whole change project; (ii) ensure that these short-term activities are coherent with the needs and priorities of the patients with dementia and their families; (iii) ensure that the team effectively celebrates the wins and publicly communicates them; (iv) explain how specific goals were reached and how other subjects could find inspiration in the project to obtain further wins; (v) communicate the benefits from the perspective of patients with dementia and their families, linking benefits to specific quick wins accomplished; (vi) emphasize the ease of short-term activity implementation; (vii) engage patients with dementia and report how they perceive the improvement in order to monitor and evaluate the accomplishments from different viewpoints; (viii) analyze wins and find alternatives that could have provided and even better accomplishment of short-term goals.

2.2.2.7 Sustain Acceleration

Kotter and Cohen (2002) highlight how quick wins can generate the side effect of having project participants believe in the success of the change process, at the detriment of a loss of urgency.

These behaviours can transform into actual traps for the success of the Change Management project. Furthermore, big changes often require long time span, especially in big organizations, and various problems could rise during following project steps and hinder the change process (Kotter 1996). Authors (Kotter & Cohen 2002) suggest this is time for *brave* and *perseverant* project participants to take action, but the cost of taking risks in order to face all potentially emerging problems. These individuals need to be provided with adequate authority, appropriate resources and sufficient time.

In the case of the health care industry, Campbell (2008) confirms that the main issue emerged when workers start to lose their sense of urgency towards the shared vision. It is the duty of the guiding coalition to keep the employees motivated. This can be achieved by evaluating external factors and comparing the current state of the process/organization/technology with challenging benchmarks, such as an incumbent competitor. By realizing that a competing company is more advanced, group cohesion is strengthened and sense of urgency increased. Furthermore, it is important to highlight how change is still not fully implemented and losing momentum could be detrimental for the whole change initiative.

An example of this last element is provided by Campbell (2008) as part of the implementation of a computerized physician order entry system. Here, it proved of great usefulness to show project participants how the change process was not completed solely with the introduction of the system. Therefore, the healthcare organization created a special team called “the red coats”. They were trained on the computerized physician order entry system and on the resolution of conflicts. Whenever physicians had a problem with the system “the red coats” were called to solve it. “The red coats” also investigated any system malfunction and verified whether the problem was due to the user or to the system itself. This helped creating a sense of constant acceleration and ongoing change, which quickly spread throughout project participants.

Auguste (2013) shows how, as part of the digital transformation of an Orthopaedic Surgical Practice Group, the sense of urgency was maintained through the constant exchange of feedbacks from and within the department of health records, which was bestowed with the responsibility to confirm the completion of the integration between clinic and hospital.

Bartholomew et al. (2014) recommend to: (i) examine every activity/project in order to understand what needs being improved; (ii) "stretch goals" or, in other words, try to extend the perceived duration of quick wins; (iii) continuously define new short-term goals in order to build momentum; (iv) continuously check the identified priorities or new ideas emerging from change recipients (as part of the author's project, these were dementia-affected patients and their families); (v) verify the possibility to include other people in the guiding team; (vi) check similar activities carried out by other organizations operating within the same context.

2.2.2.8 Institute Change

The lifeblood of change is the creation of a new and widespread organizational culture. This forms the basis for the definition of new ways of acting and operating within the organization (Kotter & Cohen 2002). This process of culture creation can be tremendously demanding because it requires the alteration of the precedent company culture. Some cultures are deeply rooted in people's minds; therefore it can prove difficult to transit towards a new state.

Nevertheless, people can be extremely successful in devising new cultures. According to the authors (Kotter & Cohen 2002), the most widespread problems in nowadays company prevent the consolidation of a single culture: high employee turnovers, crises and business pressure ensure that a defined culture hardly takes root.

In many competitive environments, the culture of the organization could be also changed in order to alter behaviours and habits of the people. However, Kotter & Cohen (2002) mention that culture change should come last. The culture of an organization should change automatically when a new way of operating has been chosen to succeed to the existing approach. Authors also suggest that there are several ways to reinforce fragile cultures, such as assigning promotions to workers that embody the new culture in relevant and visible positions, or highlighting the reason of expected success of the new organizational culture.

Campbell (2008) suggests that the adoption of EHR or other digital solutions within a healthcare organization should be preceded by preparatory elements, such as the communication of facts proving how the new solution and the bestowing of rewards for employees supporting and fostering change.

The author also provides an example on the development and improvement of a new culture in the presence of new technology. The introduction of a computerized physician order entry was followed by a practice called "Post Live". In this, experts supported physicians in their continuous improvement of the way they interacted with the new technology, promoting an "ICT-friendly" culture within the whole organization.

Auguste (2013) suggests to develop a culture of digital practice via weekly e-mails on “tips and tricks” regarding the use of an EMR. These data were collected by the “administrative champion” and consolidated during monthly staff meetings.

Furthermore, commitment was spread by having employees shredding paper-based records during the event celebrating the achieved digital transformation. This act symbolized the “destruction” of the old “paper-based” culture.

Bartholomew et al. (2014), recommend to: (i) communicate the progress and successes through various channels; (ii) embed knowledge acquired by team members within their organizations and their training programs; (iii) ensure the recognition of workers who directly promoted change; (iv) ensure the possibility to replace change leaders if they leave the organization; (v) engage patients with dementia in communication, to ensure their role in the new organizational culture.

2.2.3 Accelerating Change and the Continuous Improvement Model

Lewin’s model is particularly useful to understand the general structuring of a change process, focusing on the improvement on the state-of-the-art of a process, activity or organization. This vision of change is usually focused on a single instance of change and doesn’t perceive a cyclic and *in becoming* process.

Kotter’s recent models (2012; 2014) attempt to overcome these limitations introducing a more dynamic process. All the steps supporting change should be carried out as part of a *continuum*, and the overall process should be encapsulated in a network supporting flexibility and communication among actors. Furthermore, the author introduces the concept of four principles for the successful acceleration of change:

1. **Running the change steps concurrently and continuously:** while the original Kotter’s model focused on responding to or affecting episodic changes as part of rigid, finite and sequential steps, the Kotter’s model for accelerating change focuses on a leaner and simpler take on change;
2. **Forming a large volunteer army from up, down and across the organization** to serve as the change engine: while Kotter’s original model focused on the involvement of all stakeholders, it still had at its core a small, powerful nexus of individual leading and devising the change process; Kotter’s new take on change heavily focuses on a cross-organizational *army* of individual shaping changes all throughout the organization;
3. **Flexibly and agilely functioning in a network outside of**, but in conjunction with, **a traditional hierarchy:** Kotter’s original model was only partially tackling the theme of organizational disruption and mostly focused on the implementation of change in the presence of a traditional hierarchy; Kotter’s model for accelerating change perceives the need of an external network, working in close contact with

the existing hierarchies, but possessing a more flexible and agile network, for an adaptive management of change;

4. Operating as if change were a dynamic force, by **constantly seeking opportunities, identifying initiatives to capitalize on and complete quickly and efficiently**; while Kotter’s traditional model was mostly focused on a single instance of change at a time, its later version takes into consideration the importance of perceiving change as a fluid and constant entity, providing various opportunities throughout the process.

The following picture presents a scheme of this model for accelerating change (Kotter, 2014), which, despite bearing similarities with his previous model (Kotter, 1996), introduces a more dynamic perspective to the acceleration – and not only management – of change.

Figure 5 - Kotter’s model for accelerating change⁴

A different approach to change was suggested by Shewhart (1980) first and by Deming (2000) later, who both devised and elaborated on a fully cyclical way to perceive and drive change, by defining and adopting a continuous process of learning and improvement. Also known as the *Plan-Do-Study-Act* (PDSA) Cycle, it is characterized by four main activities, intended to be carried out to introduce, implement, design and consolidate a new product or process, as presented in the following picture.

⁴ Kotter, J.P., 2012. *Accelerate!* Harvard Business Review, 90(11), pp.45–58

Figure 6 - Deming's continuous improvement model⁵

The PDSA Cycle is always initiated by the generation and introduction of a product or process improvement idea, starting the cyclic process of continuous improvement. The activities then follow a cyclic process, including:

1. **Plan:** it deals with the planning of all the required activities regarding the introduction of the devised improvement; this preparatory activity is extremely relevant, as an ineffective activity plan could be detrimental to the success of the entire improvement:
 - a. The first action to be performed is usually the evaluation and choice between all available improvement options. Much like Kotter's and Lewin's model, pros and cons are evaluated;
 - b. Once the choice has been made, it is possible to build a change-responsible team, much like in Kotter's eight-step model;
 - c. The sharing of a strategic vision and detailing of an action plan is the final activity of this step; this includes the definition of expected results of change;
2. **Do:** this step refers to the implementation of the choices during planning (Deming 2000); Bartezzaghi (2010) suggests to follow an experimental approach, through the introduction of a single change at a time, in order to effectively evaluate its impact on the overall impacted project or process; the step itself is structured as Lewin's *Change* step, as presented in Section 2.2.1.2, with a higher focus on the

⁵ Deming, W.E., 2000. *The New Economics: For Industry, Government, Education*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for advanced engineering study.

- importance of measuring affected performances and characteristics of the product or process, while performing change;
3. **Study:** this step it deals with the analysis of the results regarding the performed activities; measurements collected during the *Do* activity are compared against expected results from the *Plan* step; ascertaining differences will support further changes and following activities (Shewhart 1980);
 4. **Act:** starting from obtained results during the *Study* phase, the decision makers choose among the following alternatives:
 - a. Adopt the change; in this case, this activity focuses on the consolidation and reutilization of change and is therefore equivalent to Lewin's model *Freeing* step (Bartezzaghi 2010);
 - b. Abandon the change;
 - c. Start the cycle again from the *Plan* activity, altering some elements of uncertainty (e.g.: contextual conditions, involved stakeholders, regulatory issues, etc); depending on the nature of change, multiple cycles could be considered desirable for an effective transformation (Deming 2000);

The first three steps are strictly related to an idea of underlining learning process. Furthermore, the concept of *Study* itself recalls the importance of knowledge generation requiring preliminary forecasts on improvements produced by change. Langley et al. (2009) put heavy emphasis on the importance of this preliminary study activity and in the anticipated envisioning of change results.

Langley et al. (2009), building from Deming's model, introduced the use of three questions, meant to be answered before starting the cycle:

1. *What are we trying to accomplish?*
2. *How will we know that a change is an improvement?*
3. *What change can we make that will result in improvement?*

Furthermore, the authors synthesized the key elements that should be taken into consideration within each step of the cycle:

1. Plan:
 - a. Goal
 - b. Questions and forecasts (*reason why*)
 - c. Plan to carry out the cycle (*who, what, where, when*)
 - d. Plan for the collection of data
2. Do:
 - a. Execution of the plan
 - b. Report issues and unpredicted results
 - c. Begin data analysis
3. Study:
 - a. Finish data analysis
 - b. Analyze differences between data and forecasts

- c. Synthesize all the elements regarding the learning process
4. Act:
 - a. What changes are needed?
 - b. Start the cycle again?

Bartezzaghi (2010), in order to support the steps of *Plan* and *Study*, suggests the adoption of seven basic quality tools, as originally designed by Ishikawa (1985):

1. Cause-and-effect diagram, or Ishikawa Diagram, or Fishbone Diagram, to collect and cluster all the possible causes of a specific problem;
2. Check sheet, to collect all available data, describe the evolution of a phenomenon/problem and quantify its characteristics affected by the investigated variables;
3. Control charts, to present how the process of product is expected to change over time;
4. Histograms, to evaluate quantitative distributions of relevant data and phenomena;
5. Pareto Chart, to illustrate priorities between assessed elements and prioritize critical factors;
6. Scatter plot, to assess correlation between variables;
7. Stratification, a classification of collected data in sub-categories in order to identify explanatory variables of the analyzed phenomena.

2.2.4 Considerations on analyzed literature and cross-step synergies

The Change Management models described by Lewin and Kotter are useful to schematize the key activities required to effectively manage a change project.

Kotter's eight step model collects all the tangible and non-tangible elements to take into account before and during the change process – e.g.: sense of urgency, vision, strategy, quick wins, culture, team working, communication etc. All these elements are strongly interrelated and this allows the completion of a step to provide valuable inputs for the accomplishment of the following – e.g.: the effective communication of a short-term win affects the creation and sustainment of the sense of urgency; the choice of adequate team members influences the probability of success regarding quick wins.

The following bullet points summarizes notable evidences emerging from literature, which will guide the definition of guidelines as part of Section 4.

1. **Unfreeze** – From the perception of a need to be addressed and the related sense of urgency infused through various alternatives, key aspects shared among authors include:
 - a. The importance of creating a sense of urgency, otherwise the change might not take place of it could not be successful;
 - b. The value of a multidisciplinary team, involving many stakeholders from various areas of competence;

- c. The importance of identifying champions and leaders;
 - d. The need for a clear vision and the importance of developing a plan including the identification of roles, responsibilities and goals;
2. **Change** – Communication of the vision, reduction of barriers and creation of quick wins are fundamental steps for the management of change; authors detailed key aspects, including:
 - a. The importance of using multiple communication channel;
 - b. The sharing of motivating facts and stories and the choice of adequate spokespersons - e.g.: patients within healthcare environments;
 - c. The importance of rewarding people who are responsible for the success;
 - d. The possibility to adopt the *see-feel-change method* to support the acknowledgement of the need and value of change;
 - e. The importance of quick wins, of accomplishing them and of communicating every success.
3. **Freezing** – The last two steps of Kotter’s model focus on the importance of providing stability of change; starting from real experiences, authors confirmed the theoretical practices, by means of:
 - a. The conservation of a strong sense of urgency among all involved subjects;
 - b. The importance of updating participants on progresses and expected benefits;
 - c. The recognition and rewarding of stakeholders and personnel responsible for the fruitful management of change.

3 Cultural and Nation-specific inputs to Change Management in the Project

To define the cultural and nation-specific inputs to the Change Management aspect regarding the DECI project, the Hofstede’s six cultural dimensions’ framework and Ferraro’s equality-hierarchy dimension were used to identify the cultural aspects of the four pilot sites, as well as insights provided by the DECI project teams based on their professional experience and personal cultural awareness. These additional insights have been detailed as complementary perspectives to Hofstede’s model and are hereby presented as inputs for the practical design of the DECI Pilot Project, to be performed as part of Project Work Package 5.

It is of significant importance to study the cultural specifics of the countries involved in the DECI project, since that might affect the result of the project and thus should be considered in the Change Management process⁶.

⁶ Further non-cultural characteristics are not discussed as part of this Deliverable. Change-affecting elements, including technology-focused perspectives, (e.g.: lack of widespread Internet connection) will be evaluated as part of Pilot Projects design.

Hofstede's six cultural dimensions' framework

There are many definitions of cultures but Hofstede describes it as follows: "Culture is the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from others" (Hofstede, 2005). This means that culture is what people in a specific society share in terms of mindsets and behaviour, even though all humans are individuals. The purpose of adapting Change Management to culture is to make it fit as many individuals as possible in a society and thus increasing the chance of successful adoption of the project results.

To be able to determine the differences between the culture of different nations Hofstede has developed six different dimensions describing the general mindset and the behaviour of the nation. The mapping was first based on a survey database created by IBM containing 100'000 surveys from over 50 countries collected in the 1970's. But the database has been updated continuously up until today. In the six dimensions all countries are mapped against each other on a scale from 0-100. There is no "best position" in any of the dimensions and thus it doesn't have to be better to be placed high on a dimension. The dimensions are societal and not individual characteristics. The six different dimensions are described below.

- **Power distance:** Is defined as the extent to which less powerful individuals in an organization accept that power is distributed unequally. A higher score equals higher acceptance (Hofstede, 2011).
- **Individualism:** Is the degree to which individuals in a society are integrated into groups. A low score indicates individualism that means that the ties between individuals are loose. A high score indicates collectivism and here the ties are strong (Hofstede, 2011).
- **Masculinity – Femininity:** In a masculinity society there are maximum emotional and social role differentiation between the genders and in femininity societies it's a minimum differentiation. A high score indicates masculinity (Hofstede, 2011).
- **Uncertainty avoidance:** Deals with a society's tolerance for ambiguity. This dimension indicates if a culture's individuals are uncomfortable or comfortable in unexpected situations. A high score equals uncomfortable to unexpected situations (Hofstede, 2011).
- **Long-term vs. short-term orientation:** In long-term oriented societies the mind-set is that the most important events in life will occur in the future and individuals adapt to changing circumstances. In short-term oriented societies the most important events take place now and individuals prefer steadiness and stability. A high score equals long-term orientation (Hofstede, 2011).
- **Indulgence vs. restraint:** In an indulgent society there is a perception of life control and people declare themselves very happy. In a restrained society there is perception helplessness and individuals don't consider themselves to be very happy (Hofstede, 2011).

The following table presents updated Hofstede’s model characteristics for the four countries hosting a Pilot Project within DECI.

Figure 7 - Cultural dimensions of pilot sites illustrated (Hofstede framework)⁷

Equality-Hierarchy dimension

The equality-hierarchy dimension brings the following question: How should individuals with different levels of power, prestige, and status interact with one another: equally or unequally? For instance, in the countries that are promoting equality the differences in power and status are aimed to be minimal in everyday life. Power is usually more diffused, personas at the higher positions can be questioned and consulted by subordinates. The relations among people are pretty informal even in different levels of power, and protocol tends to be avoided. On the other side, countries that nurture hierarchical societies, maintain status and power hierarchy. People holding higher positions are treated with great deference by those having lower positions. Bosses should not be questioned and privileges related to the roles are appreciated and respected.

⁷ The Hofstede Centre, 2015, Helsinki

Ferraro (2006) suggests to analyze cultural differences in the attributes defined in the table below to the equality-hierarchy dimensions. Each DECI pilot site has provided the opinions regarding the aspects of equality-hierarchy dimension by marking the relevant cultural attributes in the table.

<i>Egalitarian Societies</i>	<i>Hierarchical Societies</i>
<i>Low-status differences</i>	<i>High-status-differences</i>
<i>Power diffused to many people</i>	<i>Power concentrated with few people</i>
<i>Delegation of authority</i>	<i>Little delegation of authority</i>
<i>Informal social relations</i>	<i>Formal social relations</i>
<i>Minimum deference for superiors</i>	<i>Maximum deference for superiors</i>
<i>Superiors can be questioned</i>	<i>Superiors cannot be questioned</i>
<i>Little respect for old age</i>	<i>Great respect for old age</i>
<i>Mechanisms to redress grievances</i>	<i>No mechanism to redress grievances</i>

Table 1 – Equality-Hierarchy dimension⁸

Based on the frameworks discussed above, the following chapters represent the cultural characteristics of each DECI pilot country. Each of the following sections has been populated with insights based on Hofstede’s cultural dimensions’ framework, tackling the perspective of local environments, thanks to the direct involvement of DECI Local Partners and the gathering of care management experiences that bear cultural relevance.

3.1 Cultural Characteristics of Israel

Based on Hofstede framework, the following description reflects the cultural characteristics of Israel per each dimension. Additional insights have been added by the Project team from Israel.

⁸ Ferraro, G., 2006. *The cultural dimension of international business*, Fifth edition, Pearson Prentice Hall.

Figure 8 – Israel's scores in Hofstede's model⁷

- **Power distance (13 points):** In Israel independency, equal rights, accessible superiors and decentralization of power are important.
- **Individualism (54 points):** The Israeli society is a blend of individualist and collectivistic cultures. Small families with a focus on parent-children relationship are common. Communication is direct and expressive.
 - Additional insights provided by the project team: society pays a strong emphasis on family and ties with close friends, while permitting self-expression.
- **Masculinity (47 points):** Israel isn't a clear masculine or feminine society. However, performance is highly valued and managers are expected to be decisive.
 - Additional insights provided by the project team: Although there is complete freedom for women to choose their occupation, women are encouraged to assume more traditional female roles. Women and men alike face strong societal expectations to have children. However, women are in most cases the ones to play the key role in child rearing.
- **Uncertainty avoidance (81 points):** Israel has strong uncertainty avoidance and thus, there is an emotional need for rules, precision and punctuality and security is an important element.
- **Long term orientation (38 points):** Israel's relatively low score here means that the culture implies that the mindset is normative. Thus, there is a great respect for

traditions, a small tendency to save for the future and a focus on achieving quick results.

- **Indulgence:** There is currently no data for Israel in this dimension.

The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the Israeli culture according to Ferraro’s model. The compiling of the following table has been performed by Local Partners, based on the characteristics of the model and their experiences within the Pilot Project environment. Bolded cells identify relevant dimensions according to Ferraro’s model.

Egalitarian Societies	Hierarchical Societies
<i>Low-status differences</i>	<i>High-status-differences</i>
<i>Power diffused to many people</i>	Power concentrated with few people
<i>Delegation of authority</i>	<i>Little delegation of authority</i>
Informal social relations	<i>Formal social relations</i>
Minimum deference for superiors	<i>Maximum deference for superiors</i>
Superiors can be questioned	<i>Superiors cannot be questioned</i>
Little respect for old age	<i>Great respect for old age</i>
Mechanisms to redress grievances	<i>No mechanism to redress grievances</i>

Table 2 – Equality-Hierarchy dimension of Israel

3.2 Cultural Characteristics of Italy

Based on Hofstede framework, the following description reflects the cultural characteristics of Italy per each dimension. Additional insights have been added by the Project team from Italy.

Figure 9 – Italy's scores in Hofstede's model⁷

- **Power distance (50 points):** Italy tends to prefer equality and decentralization of power and decision-making. The younger generation tends to prefer teamwork and an open management more than the older generation.
 - Additional insights provided by project team: Italy tends to favour hierarchical structures, which are often present and respected, especially within large organizations and other work environments. Older generations tend to adhere more easily to this form of hierarchies, while younger generations tend to prefer teamwork, peer-based approaches and an open management.
- **Individualism (76 points):** With a high score here Italy is an individualist culture and personal ideas and objectives in life are very motivating and personal fulfilment is important. Even though the society is individualistic, importance is put on family and friends.
 - Additional insights provided by project team: Italy is an individualist culture and personal ideas and objectives in life are very motivating and personal fulfilment is perceived as important. Even though the society is strongly individualistic, great importance is put on family and friends, while larger formal networks tend to be less privileged and sought after.
- **Masculinity (70 points):** Italy is highly success oriented and driven. Competition is seen as good and winning is important in one's life.
 - Additional insights provided by project team: Italy is highly success oriented and driven. Competition is seen as good and winning is important in one's life. Differentiation among genders is strongly perceived, despite

recent cultural trends showing an attempt to grant a more equal perception among genders.

- **Uncertainty avoidance (75 points):** Italy's high score in this dimension means that as a nation Italians are not comfortable in ambiguous situations. Formality is important and to avoid uncertainty a lot of effort is put into detailed planning.
 - Additional insights provided by project team: Italy's high score in this dimension means that as a nation Italians are not comfortable in ambiguous situations. Formality is still perceived as important and to avoid uncertainty a lot of effort is put into detailed planning.
- **Long term orientation (61 points):** Italy is a pragmatic culture. Thus, it is easy for them to adapt tradition to changed conditions, they have a tendency to save and they show perseverance in achieving results.
 - Additional insights provided by project team: Italy is a pragmatic culture, as well as a strongly tradition-centred country: its future-focused mentality can be easily overshadowed by cultural aspects handed down from the past.
- **Indulgence (30 points):** A low score in this dimension have a tendency to cynicism and pessimism. Individuals can feel that indulging themselves is somewhat wrong.

A number of additional insights have been added by the Project team from Italy introducing new dimensions for discussion. These have been detailed as complementary perspectives starting from Hofstede's and Ferraro's model, detailing additional cultural perspective that are perceived as strongly relevant within the Pilot Project environment:

- Strong respect for the elderly: Respect for older people, both in work environments and within personal life, is a very strong component, which can lead to implicit and spontaneous deference towards older colleagues and managers, as well as regard and care for elderly relatives.
- Sporadic diffidence towards technology: Compared to other European Countries, Italians – especially older citizens – can show a tendency of diffidence and mistrust towards technology in general and invasive technology in particular. However, the newer generation of elderly people (called “younger elderly”) seems to be more open to the use of ICT, when compared to the previous generations of elderly. Probably, this is due to the fact that they are more used to employ technological devices during their everyday life.
- Strong separation between work and home environments: Italians tend to strongly separate private life from the work life, adopting practices and procedures that vary from very informal – with friends, family members and peers – to very formal – with superiors.
- Strong sense of family: Networks within Italians' private life tend to be strong family-centred; depending on regional characteristics, the concept of family can vary from a small network of individuals (roughly in the society of the north part

of the country) to larger groups of relatives (roughly in the societies of the centre and south part of the country).

The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the Italian culture according to Ferraro’s model. The compiling of the following table has been performed by Local Partners, based on the characteristics of the model and their experiences within the Pilot Project environment. Bolded cells identify relevant dimensions according to Ferraro’s model.

Egalitarian Societies	Hierarchical Societies
<i>Low-status differences</i>	High-status-differences
<i>Power diffused to many people</i>	Power concentrated with few people
<i>Delegation of authority</i>	Little delegation of authority
Informal social relations	<i>Formal social relations</i>
<i>Minimum deference for superiors</i>	Maximum deference for superiors
<i>Superiors can be questioned</i>	Superiors cannot be questioned
<i>Little respect for old age</i>	Great respect for old age
<i>Mechanisms to redress grievances</i>	No mechanism to redress grievances

Table 3 – Equality-Hierarchy dimension of Italy

- Hierarchy is often a very strong component of business relations, and many Italian organizations tend to favour implicit procedures for the management of communications and relations between leaders and subordinates.
- On the other side, social and personal relationships are usually very informal and can present various degrees of freedom, when compared to work-focused communications.
- Respect for older people, both in work environments and within personal life, is a very strong component, which can lead to implicit and spontaneous deference towards older colleagues and managers, as well as regard and care for elderly relatives.

3.3 Cultural Characteristics of Spain

Based on Hofstede framework, the following description reflects the cultural characteristics of Spain per each dimension.

Figure 10 – Spain's scores in Hofstede's model⁷

- **Power distance (57 points):** Spain's high score in this dimension indicates that it is a hierarchical society. Thus the people here accept a hierarchical order in which everybody has a place. Subordinates expect to be told what to do.
- **Individualism (51 points):** Spain is a collectivist society, this means that teamwork is natural and employees tend to work in this way without the need of motivation from management.
- **Masculinity (42 points):** Spain's relatively low score here means that excessive competitiveness and polarization are not appreciated. Managers tend to consult their subordinates to know their opinions and base their decisions on this.
- **Uncertainty avoidance (86 points):** Spain's very high score here implies that confrontation is avoided as it causes stress and scales up to the personal level very quickly. There is a great concern for changing and ambiguous situations.
- **Long-term orientation (48 points):** Spain is a normative country and thus people prefer to live in the moment without a great concern for the future. People tend to look for quick results without any delays.
- **Indulgence (44 points):** With a low score Spain is not an indulgent society. Thus people have a tendency to cynicism and pessimism. Individuals can feel that indulging themselves is somewhat wrong.

A number of additional insights have been added by the Project team from Spain introducing new dimensions for discussion. These have been detailed as complementary perspectives starting from Hofstede’s and Ferraro’s model, detailing additional cultural perspective that are perceived as strongly relevant within the Pilot Project environment:

- Readiness to change: Older workers are reluctant to change old ways, especially regarding technological change.
- High level of bureaucracy: In informal interviews, doctors have expressed that the high level of bureaucracy prevents them to dedicate more time to patients.
- Low culture of innovation: In general, health professionals have three kind of activities: care, teaching and research. Nevertheless, care takes most of the healthcare professional’s time, and research is not highly valued, both in professional and economic terms.
- Informal relationship with patients: Younger generations have relatively less respect to professionals such as teachers or doctors. In informal interviews, some doctors have expressed that many patients express feelings such as “I am paying your salary, so you work for me”.

The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the Spanish culture according to Ferraro’s model. The compiling of the following table has been performed by Local Partners, based on the characteristics of the model and their experiences within the Pilot Project environment. Bolded cells identify relevant dimensions according to Ferraro’s model.

Egalitarian Societies	Hierarchical Societies
<i>Low-status differences</i>	High-status-differences
<i>Power diffused to many people</i>	Power concentrated with few people
<i>Delegation of authority</i>	Little delegation of authority
Informal social relations	<i>Formal social relations</i>
Minimum deference for superiors	<i>Maximum deference for superiors</i>
<i>Superiors can be questioned</i>	Superiors cannot be questioned
Little respect for old age	<i>Great respect for old age</i>
Mechanisms to redress grievances	<i>No mechanism to redress grievances</i>

Table 4 – Equality-Hierarchy dimension of Spain

- Some of these expressions are too extreme, and in some points Spanish culture lies somewhere in the middle.
- Older adults in Spain play an important role within families. Within organizations, work laws used to make it difficult to replace older workers, but nowadays some of them are being replaced by younger workers, much cheaper but with much more less experience. Economic cuts and new work laws have led many enterprises to dispose older workers with experience, leading to some structures of “bosses and scholarships”, leading to high status differences within companies.
- In Spain, most work relationships are mediated by personal relationships, it is not very common to have exclusively professional relationships. As an example, grievances are usually addressed informally, through direct conversations among affected parties.

3.4 Cultural Characteristics of Sweden

Based on Hofstede framework, the following description reflects the cultural characteristics of Sweden per each dimension.

Figure 11 – Sweden’s scores in Hofstede’s model⁷

- **Power distance (31 points):** Sweden’s low score means that people are independent, hierarchy is only for convenience, equal rights is important, superiors are accessible and the relation with them is informal and employees expect to be consulted. Communication is direct and participative.

- **Individualism (71 points):** Sweden is an individualist society. Thus people are only expected to take care of themselves and their immediate families. Offence causes guilt and a loss of self-esteem.
- **Masculinity (5 points):** Sweden is a feminine society. This means that managers should be supportive and decision-making is achieved through involvement. Conflicts are resolved through negotiations.
- **Uncertainty avoidance (29 points):** Sweden has a low score here that indicates that practice counts more than principles. People believe there should not be more rules than necessary and if they are ambiguous they should be changed. Innovation is welcomed.
- **Long term orientation (53 points):** Sweden’s intermediate score entails no clear preference in this dimension.
- **Indulgence (78 points):** Sweden is a culture of indulgence. This means that people exhibit a willingness to realize their impulses and have fun.

The following table summarizes the main characteristics of the Swedish culture according to Ferraro’s model. The compiling of the following table has been performed by Local Partners, based on the characteristics of the model and their experiences within the Pilot Project environment. Bolded cells identify relevant dimensions according to Ferraro’s model.

Egalitarian Societies	Hierarchical Societies
Low-status differences	<i>High-status-differences</i>
Power diffused to many people	<i>Power concentrated with few people</i>
Delegation of authority	<i>Little delegation of authority</i>
Informal social relations	<i>Formal social relations</i>
Minimum deference for superiors	<i>Maximum deference for superiors</i>
Superiors can be questioned	<i>Superiors cannot be questioned</i>
Little respect for old age	<i>Great respect for old age</i>
Mechanisms to redress grievances	<i>No mechanism to redress grievances</i>

Table 5 – Equality-Hierarchy dimension of Sweden

4 Change Management Guidelines for the Implementation of DECI's Digital Solutions

Starting from the literature analysis presented in Section 2 and the local perspectives examined in Section 3, it is possible to detail a set of general guidelines to support Change Management activities within the process. Section 4.1 details a list of practices and insights derived from the literature analysis and the evaluation of real cases, while the following sub-sections, within chapter 4.2, elaborate on the regional characteristics presented in Section 3.

Because this document is finalized before the actual design of the DECI Pilot Projects, these guidelines are to be considered as a set of non-pilot specific and non-technology-specific suggestions, to be taken into consideration when devising the structure of each Pilot Project during further Project activities.

4.1 Change Management Guidelines in Healthcare Environments

Starting from Kotter's eight-step model, the following list details a set of general guidelines emerged from literature analyses, with an eye for both theoretical recommendations from leading authors and healthcare-specific perspectives:

1. Create a sense of urgency:

- a. The creation of a sense of urgency within the DECI Project will be ensured by the strong involvement of external stakeholders within Project activities, beginning with the initial Pilot-base analyses; these subjects include doctors, nurses and other hospital personnel, as well as patients representatives, family members and informal caregivers, who possess a clear perception of the most important characteristics of the existing care and assistance processes and can provide insights on care and patients' needs within the targeted processes;
- b. These subjects have already been involved in Co-Creation Workshop (CCW) activities and Local Brainstorming (LBS) activities, therefore contributing directly to the Project's evolution;
- c. Local Partners will keep these subjects involved in further activities – when appropriate – providing a clear perspective on what will happen as part of Pilot Project activities, what needs will be answered and how change-related activities fall into place in the big picture of the DECI Project;
- d. Provision of information to involved external stakeholders will lay on quantitative parameters and information – when available – so as to provide a clear and measurable vision on how and at what level of detail identified needs will be answered;
- e. Further activities will foresee the activation of dialogues with interested stakeholders and, to further support the creation of a sense of urgency, communication activities will be managed from a patient perspective –

when possible – (e.g.: Scenario-Based Design as part of Local Brainstorming Activities);

2. Build a guiding coalition:

- a. The informal *guiding coalition* within each Pilot Project will be formed by DECI Project members – who will directly interact with all involved external subjects – and a number of external stakeholders directly involved in the change-affected process; partition between these two groups can either be formal – therefore creating two parallel coalition, one with DECI personnel and the other with local stakeholders – or informal – therefore devising a single guiding group –, depending on local characteristics;
- b. Depending on each Pilot Projects’ characteristics, local Partners will be encouraged to identify competent and learned individuals who will be strongly affected by the implemented changes (e.g.: doctors, nurses, family members of patients) and who strongly believe in the need for change; these individuals could be part of the external stakeholders involved during CCWs and LBSs at each local site;
- c. Informal selection and involvement of these subjects should be performed in accordance with individuals’ characteristics and competences, with the aim of instituting a *coalition* of complementary capabilities and perspectives, integrating competences and viewpoints brought by DECI Project Partners;
- d. The informal identification of one or more *champions* is strongly suggested: these subjects, either from within the DECI Project or emerging from the interested stakeholders, will be one of the main driving forces for the implementation of change, sharing their vision and commitment with all involved stakeholders;
- e. To ensure the identification of a strong *coalition* and of one or more *champions*, local Partners will be encouraged to involve large portions of pilot-sites staff in participative actions within the Project, according to each organization’s availabilities;

3. Form a strategic vision and initiative:

- a. The generation of a long term vision will be accomplished with a clear identification and dissemination of the change initiatives to implement; thanks to a deep involvement of the aforementioned *coalition* and *champions*, a DECI-external perspective will be ensured, to validate the importance and need for change;
- b. Devised change will be detailed and disseminated in accordance to patients’ and stakeholders’ perspectives, therefore ensuring the overall change vision is coherent with individuals’ priorities and has a direct impact on all stakeholders’ needs;
- c. Moreover, the vision will be translated into tangible benefits that are expected to surface thanks to the implementation of change; these benefits

will be strongly connected to KPIs that will be monitored throughout the change process;

- d. Local Brainstorming Activities within each Pilot Site have been strongly focused on the definition of external-stakeholders-generated desired scenarios; these will inspire design of the finalized Pilot Projects and will ensure strong commitment and involvement of stakeholders towards the change vision;

4. Enlist a volunteer army:

- a. The broadening of the *coalition* will be ensured thanks to a continuous set of dissemination actions, which will make sure all Pilot Sites organizations are aware of the change process and are willing to contribute with it;
- b. Informal comments and suggestions will be gathered from interested participants – including non-stakeholders – to guarantee that a large audience is consulted; the external stakeholders joining the *coalition* will be requested to gather off-the-record comments from their colleagues – when possible;
- c. The usage of automatic communication tools outside of the Pilot Sites’ environments will support external awareness towards the initiatives; participation in international conferences and meetings, scientific disseminations as part of journals and specialized websites and presentation of the initiative throughout online channels will be ensured;
- d. Building from step 3 of Kotter’s model, the dissemination activities will be performed – when possible – with a strong patient-centric and scenario-based perspective, therefore ensuring that a sense of urgency is maintained within involved subjects and the initiatives can be clearly understood by non-specialized individuals;
- e. Internal communication among the *coalition*, the *champions* and the *army* will be maintained throughout the change process;

5. Enable action by removing barrier:

- a. With a case-by-case perspective, Local Partners will ensure the removal of barriers according to change practices suggested by literature; these include:
 - i. The enforcement of a participative approach involving resisting individuals;
 - ii. The introduction of incentives towards committed individuals;
 - iii. The institution of dialogues between resisting individuals, committed stakeholders and people in need (e.g.: patients’ relatives or caregivers);
- b. The *coalition* and the *champions* will play a key role in the removal of barriers, as they will be required to act as promoters and enforcers of the change initiatives within the targeted environment; these subjects will also possess a unique perspective on both the change initiative and the targeted

organization and can, therefore, moderate dialogues between diffident and interested individuals;

- c. Aforementioned dissemination activities will be exploited to grant transparency on the initiative, providing information to all interested individuals;
- d. Dissemination activities will also be performed with a cross-Pilot approach, showing resisting individuals how a concerted change initiative is being performed, as part of the DECI Project, within other countries; emphasis will be put in the results achieved by every country, providing valuable information on care and assistance process improvements within the DEC ecosystem;

6. Generate Short-term wins:

- a. In conjunction with dissemination activities and stakeholders involvements, short-term milestones will be defined, in order to guarantee that commitment is maintained all throughout the initiative and the *guiding coalition* is able to monitor change progression throughout predetermined checkpoints;
- b. These milestones will be defined at a general level based on Pilot Project designs, but can also be customized according to each Pilot Site needs: emphasis will be put in a critical analysis of this milestones, so as to further steer change towards an improvement of the present conditions, adjusting the initiative when needed;
- c. Milestones and related short-term wins will also serve the purpose of attracting further subjects towards the Project, as they will be treated – when possible – as moments of external dissemination of good Project intermediate results;
- d. Short-term wins will be exploited as an important dissemination opportunity, as they will allow to present to both targeted organizations and the public what benefits the change processes are introducing; as stated in point 4 of Kotter’s model, both online and offline channels will be exploited; a detailed description of how the win was achieved will be provided;
- e. These wins will be coherent with the scope of the defined vision, therefore tackling the theme of care and assistance process improvement from patients’, caregivers’ and other stakeholders’ perspectives;

7. Sustain acceleration:

- a. Constant and mutual feedbacks between various Pilot Sites will contribute in the sustainment of acceleration throughout the change process; while not explicitly supporting a competitive mood between the four Pilot Projects, using comparable aspects as valuable benchmark can push local participants to maintain a high level of commitment towards the initiative;

- b. The *coalition* and the *champions* will be tasked with supporting the retention of a high level of commitment within both involved and interested subjects; starting from the aforementioned short-term wins, it will be crucial to have them not only stress the good results obtained, but also insist on the importance of keeping up with a high level of involvement;
- c. Thanks to a large pool of stakeholders, active participants and interested subjects, continuous feedbacks will be gathered, in order to identify – as mentioned in point 6 of the model – ways to further improve on already perceivable good results;
- d. In addition, based on the obtained results and the achieved milestones, further short-term goals can be adjusted or introduced, so as to make sure all stakeholders feel challenged all throughout the process; similarly, new *champions* might be brought on board all throughout the change process;

8. Institute Change:

- a. Final-step impacts of change on cultural, organizational and other aspects will be managed in accordance to the feedbacks gathered all throughout the change initiative within each Pilot Site; the promotion of a “change-friendly” and “ICT-friendly” culture will be among the top priorities within each Pilot Site;
- b. Closing communications will be spread, both online and offline, celebrating the ending of the eight-step change process and inviting recipients – and other interested subjects – to reflect on positive, as well as negative, aspects of the initiative, providing feedbacks on the overall change process;
- c. Internal communications to disseminate results will be carried on even after the change is fully implemented; these include also the internal circulation of external disseminations (e.g.: posting articles and scientific posters within the Pilot Sites’ location, so as to continuously spread awareness on the initiative);
- d. Pilot-Sites-specific closing events will be planned, celebrating the acquired results involving all stakeholders and participating subjects; at this stage, *champions* and other strongly committed stakeholders can be rewarded for their efforts and contributions;
- e. When possible, involvements of the recipients of change not actively involved in the change initiative (e.g.: patients, informal caregivers, patients’ relatives) can have a symbolic value within closing activities and can help participants keep the focus on the value of the performed change actions.

4.2 Country-specific Change Management Guidelines

This Section includes a set of country-specific Change Management suggestions, expanding on Section 4.1 thanks to local inputs presented in Section 3.

As presented in the following sections, these guidelines tackle the specific reality of each pilot site, therefore focusing on healthcare-related and patient-centred perspectives. Each of the following sections, therefore, moves from the local characteristics that were highlighted as part of the analysis of country-specific characteristics.

For each cultural aspect emerged in Section 3, the expected impact on the Project is assessed, based on its relevance within the Pilot Sites' environments and, moreover, for patients, caregivers, healthcare organization's personnel and other stakeholders.

Once cultural aspects have been prioritized, each cultural aspect is associated to specific **barriers to the change** (Sirkin et al., 2005), which can be synthesized into two macro-category (see Figure 12):

- Individual sources of resistance, where we can find barriers such as economic factors, the fear of the unknown, a selective information of processing, etc.
- Organizational sources of resistances, such as structural inertia, threat to expertise, limited focus of change, etc.

Figure 12 – Resistance to change

Then, additional perspectives to the ones suggested in Section 4.1 are suggested for all high-impact and medium-impact cultural aspects, to support the effective management of change within each individual Pilot Sites. Please, note that the Change Management specifications detailed in the following sub-sections have been detailed and internally validated by Local Partners, merging the local-specific cultural information emerging from Section 3 with first-hand experiences within local healthcare environments.

Finally, for each cultural aspect, and the related barrier and change management specification, we defined the **needed competences to lead the change** (Kotter, 2007), intended as the preferred style/approach to adopt as change initiator to overcome the identified barriers on the correlating cultural aspect. In particular, a change leader should

have the right balance between a direct style and a participative style and between a relations oriented approach and a tasks oriented approach. This means to balance the following competences:

- *Promoting change* through convincing and communication skills;
- *Achieving the targets* through decisional and coordination skills;
- *Transforming the organization* through orientation and motivation skills;
- *Talent enhancing* through engagement and listening skills.

Figure 13 – Competences to lead the change

4.2.1 Change Management Guidelines Specifications for the Israeli Pilot Site

Change Management inputs emerging from the Israeli perspective strongly focus on communication practices and individual's mind-sets. A deep involvement of stakeholders – not to be intended as a group of people, but as individuals directly or indirectly involved in the care process – will be put into action.

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change Management specification	Needed competences to lead the change
Bottom line mentality and sense of practicality	Medium	Selective information processing Group inertia	Communication actions within the Change Management initiative need to be devised with a pragmatic approach, focusing on down-to-earth impacts and tangible benefits of change	Promoting change
Resourcefulness and participative attitude	Medium	Limited focus of change Selective information processing	Strongly involve patients' – when possible – family members, caregivers, hospital personnel and other stakeholders in the process of devising and implementing change	Transforming the organization
Accessibility and approachability, minimum deference for superiors	Medium	Group inertia	Adopt an informal approach and when presenting and disseminating change	Talent enhancing

Table 6 – Change Management guidelines specifications for the Israeli Pilot Site

4.2.2 Change Management Guidelines Specifications for the Italian Pilot Site

The Italian environment is strongly focused on traditional and family-centred values. A strong involvement of stakeholders will be performed, ensuring that not just individuals, but families and informal care and assistance networks are involved as a whole.

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change Management specification	Needed competences to lead the change
Strong innate respect for the elderly	High	Fear of unknown Limited focus of change	Have Change Management strongly gravitate around elderly people's needs and priorities, directly involve them, when possible, in the Change Process	Talent enhancing
Sporadic diffidence toward technology (especially in elderly subjects)	High	Fear of unknown Habit Limited focus of change	Foresee a non-invasive approach towards the introduction of technology within care processes; avoid Big-Bang approaches for the introduction of ICT-enabled functionalities within existing environments	Promoting change
Strong innate sense of family and belonging	High	Fear of unknown Habit	Strongly involve family members within the Change Management process, when possible; welcome feedback from family members all throughout the change process	Talent enhancing
High-status-differences	Medium	Habit Structural inertia	Strong respect is usually attributed to Doctors by family members; have Doctors be the <i>face of change</i>	Transforming the organization
Little delegation of authority	Medium	Habit Threat to established power	Put family members – especially those who already work as active subjects in informal care processes – in charge of supporting their relatives in the adoption of change	Achieving the targets

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change Management specification	Needed competences to lead the change
Informal social relations	Medium	Group inertia	Adopt a communicative, open and clearly readable strategy to promote change, involving care and social assistance authorities	Talent enhancing

Table 7 – Change Management guidelines specifications for the Italian Pilot Site

4.2.3 Change Management Guidelines Specifications for the Spanish Pilot Site

The Spanish perspective bears similarities with the Italian scenario, in the form of high levels of status difference. The unique perspective of the Spanish scenario is the central role of the patient, not just as a passive recipient of change, but also as an active and willing individual that can be tasked with various degrees of self-management activities, thanks to the promotion of a widespread change culture.

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change Management specification	Needed competences to lead the change
High level of bureaucracy	High	Structural inertia Threat to establish power	Any change in the care provision model has to undergo different levels of management, which might delay the introduction of new technologies within the Public Healthcare System	Achieving the targets
High-status-differences	Medium	Habit Structural inertia	DECI aims to promote multi-disciplinary care; roles within the platform and permissions have to be clearly defined	Transforming the organization
Readiness to change	Medium	Limited focus of change Selective information processing	Pilots should be carried out involving volunteer professionals, and the results should demonstrate an optimization of the care process	Transforming the organization

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change specification	Management	Needed competences to lead the change
Informal relationship with patients	Medium	Habit Selective information processing	The use of DECI's solution should focus on a culture change based on the self-management of patients, from <i>"doctors working for me"</i> to <i>"I'm working for myself"</i> , where the health professionals would adopt the role of a collaborator		Transforming the organization
Partial illiteracy of the population	Medium	Fear of the unknown	Spain is the only Project Pilot Site country with a literacy rate lower than 99%, with a non-critical average literacy rate of 98.1% ⁹ ; it will be important to foresee, as part of Pilot activities, the adoption of simple and non-exclusively-written forms of communication		Transforming the organization

Table 8 – Change Management guidelines specifications for the Spanish Pilot Site

4.2.4 Change Management Guidelines Specifications for the Swedish Pilot Site

The Swedish perspective strongly focuses on the importance of granting a continuous and repeated improvement process, while simultaneously removing perceived barriers. These are expected to be mostly due to a perceived distance with the decision-making authorities.

⁹ *Adult Literacy rate, population 15+ years, both sexes*. IUS Data Centre. UNESCO.

Cultural aspect	Impact	Related barriers	Change Management specification	Needed competences to lead the change
Individualism	High	Group inertia Selective information processing Limited focus of change	The process of ethical improvement is likely to be challenging; the importance of having a profound understanding of the needs and wills of cognitive impaired patients should likely be addressed in ongoing, repeated processed of improvement during different stages of patients illness and progress of DECI-pilot; this needs to be approved by ethical committee	Achieving the targets
Masculinity (perceived distance against external figures)	High	Fear of the unknown Threat to established power Structural inertia	Efforts will be spent to reduce the perceived distance in decision making in an European project, for example brainstorming meetings	Transforming the organization
Masculinity (strong sense of culture)	Medium	Habit Selective information processing Structural inertia	Introduction and explanation of different cultural aspects in DECI to find understandings of the importance of involvement (and pace) in the Swedish context	Transforming the organization

Table 9 – Change Management guidelines specifications for the Swedish Pilot Site

5 Monitoring Inputs and expected Impact of Change Management

Change Management practices detailed in Section 4 will be implemented within each Pilot Site according to local characteristics. Pilot Projects designs and implementations as part of Project Work Package 5 – and first tackled within Deliverable 1.5, which deals with the design of the final Pilot Projects, based on the pre-Pilot analyses – will address Change Management and define how to implemented these guidelines within each environment.

Monitoring of the most relevant performance indicators, on the other hand, will be performed by project Work Package 6, which will run in parallel to Pilot Projects and will investigate, among other aspects, the impact of change on the targeted environments.

Change monitoring-focused indicators will be defined as part of Work Package 6, based on the actual design of the various Pilot Sites. The following is a list of suggested preliminary indicators that can be monitored throughout following Work Package 6 activities, linked to Kotter's eight-step model:

- 1. Create a sense of urgency:**
 - a. Measurement or esteem of the level of involvement of stakeholders within local activities;
 - b. Measurement of feedbacks and contributions provided by involved stakeholders;
 - c. Measurement of the outbound information flows provided to involved stakeholders;
- 2. Building a guiding coalition:**
 - a. Measurement of the size, scope and competences of the guiding coalition;
 - b. Measurement of the level of involvement of the guiding coalition;
 - c. Measurement of the effectiveness of the guiding coalition in reaching third parties;
- 3. Form a strategic vision and initiative:**
 - a. Measurement of the level of dissemination of the change initiative to implements (e.g.: measurement of the potential and actual reach of the dissemination);
 - b. Measurement of the effectiveness and clarity of performed dissemination (e.g.: via satisfaction questionnaires to change participants);
 - c. Measurement of the clarity of communication of tangible benefits foreseen as a result of the performed change;
- 4. Enlist of a volunteer army:**
 - a. Measurement of the size, scope and competences of the volunteer army;
 - b. Measurement of the relative size – or relative increase – in the volunteer army compared to the guiding coalition;
 - c. Measurement of the effectiveness of the adopted communication channels;
 - d. Measurement of the communications between the guiding coalition, the *champions* and the volunteer army;
- 5. Enable action by removing barrier:**
 - a. Measurement of the level of involvement and participation of individuals acting within the change initiative;
 - b. Measurement of incentives attributed to participating individuals within the change initiative;
 - c. Measurement of the levels of satisfaction of participating individuals towards the change initiative and of the variation of said level;

- d. Measurement of the scope, size and potential reach of outbound communications and dissemination activities;
- 6. Generate short-term wins:**
 - a. Measurement of the successful reaching of planned milestones and investigations of potential gaps;
 - b. Measurement of the level of exploitation and dissemination of milestones and of the related achievements;
 - c. Measurement of the effectiveness of milestones dissemination and exploitation (e.g.: number of additional participants involved thanks to the dissemination of results);
 - 7. Sustain acceleration:**
 - a. Measurement of the level of involvement of participants (e.g.: via satisfaction questionnaires);
 - b. Measurement of the effectiveness, depth and reach of dissemination all throughout the initial acceleration phase and during following sustainment activities;
 - c. Measurement of the number of defective participants, of newcomers within the change initiative and of the resulting balance;
 - 8. Institute change:**
 - a. Measurement of the overall impact of change on the targeted organization (e.g.: by comparing *as is* and *to be* process effectiveness, quality, safety indicators);
 - b. Measurement of the effectiveness, depth and reach of closing communication, both inbound and outbound;
 - c. Measurement of the overall satisfaction of change participants and gathering of feedbacks for further improvement.

These measurements and the adopted indicators will serve as inspiration and input to Project Work Package 6, in conjunction with other core monitoring activities, focused on business model-related and technology-enabled functionalities implementations. In order to enable a fruitful monitoring of Change Management-oriented indicators, the suggested measures presented in this Section are expected to be further edited – or even redesigned – according to Pilot Projects’ characteristics and related monitoring practices.

6 Conclusions

Change Management practices will play an important role as part of Pilot Project activities and will be put into effect both from a general Project-wide perspective and from a Pilot Site-specific viewpoint.

Literature provides various inputs to the Project, starting from Lewin’s and Kotter’s model, which formed the general outline for the analysis and description of Change Management practices within this Deliverable. Starting from Kotter’s model, various

inputs were gathered from literature, with an eye for healthcare environments and elderly care-focused projects.

These inputs allowed the identification of various practices and insights to detail DECI-specific Change Management suggestions, to be detailed according to each Pilot Site's characteristics and change to be implemented.

Among the most relevant suggestions, as detailed in Section 4.1, are:

1. The creation of a sense of urgency and need for change, thanks to clear and pervasive communications;
2. The definition of a clear vision of change, to be disseminated as part of the initiative's execution with a strong stakeholder-based focus;
3. The structured involvement of various kinds of stakeholders, bringing diverse competences a perspectives to the initiative;
4. The provision of incentives and stimuli to both encourage participants' actions and attract newcomers to the initiative;
5. The careful removal of barriers, via the targeting of the most heart-felt resistances and restrictions within the various change-affected contexts;
6. The continuous push towards and expansion in the size of the participating group, ensuring the formation of a volunteer army;
7. The effective and continuous provision of information to and from all involved stakeholders and participants, as well as the effective gathering of feedbacks to evaluate the change initiative;
8. The focus on short-term wins and pre-scheduled milestones no be achieved, so as to ensure a constant commitment in all participants and ensure change momentum is maintained as long as possible;
9. The continuous in-depth monitoring of various pre-set indicators, to measure and evaluate the effects of change on the targeted environments;
10. The continuous dissemination of the goals of the initiative, with an easy-to-understand explanation of the targets and goals of the initiative;
11. The fruitful institution of change within the environment, with a careful evaluation of the final steps of the initiative and a promotion of a culture and lasting culture of change;
12. The perception of change as an ongoing process, lasting longer than the initiative itself and spreading outside of the targeted environment.

In parallel to a literature-inspired provision of indications and insights on Change Management within healthcare and, most notably, elderly-care-focused environments, the analysis has focused on cultural characteristics of the four environments that will be tackled by the DECI Project.

The local analysis presented in Section 3 allowed the identification of country-specific suggestions that will be exploited, during Pilot Project actions design, to specify Change

Management practices within each reality. These are briefly summarized in the following bullet points and presented in the details in Section 4.2:

1. The Israeli perspective will strongly focus on the importance of pragmatic communication actions highlighting tangible benefits of change; a strong involvement of patients, family members, caregivers and other stakeholders will also be a priority, as well as the usage of an informal approach for the dissemination of change-related aspects;
2. The Italian Pilot Project will strongly gravitate around the involvement of elderly people – and their informal care networks including families and caregivers – and MDs, as well as the envision of non-invasive approaches towards the introduction of technology-based components within the targeted environments; great importance will be attributed to the adoption of a communicative and open strategy for the promotion of change;
3. The Spanish environment will have to carefully manage bureaucratic aspects of the foreseen change, including a clear definition of the roles in the change initiative; as per the Italian site, a strong involvement of volunteers will be important, with the goal of validating the improvements in the care process; communication activities will be strongly focused on the promotion of a sense of responsibility, empowerment and self-management of care;
4. The Swedish site will require a strong focus on ethical aspects; efforts will be taken to ensure that the perceived distance against external roles and responsible figures is reduced as much as possible; change activities will be tailored around needs and wills of cognitive impaired individuals, thanks to a process of continuous evaluation.

Finally, regarding the preliminary indicators suggested in the Section 5, please note that the most relevant ones will be settled and monitored within the WP6 “Evaluation of business, industrial and quality impacts”.

7 References

- Auguste, J., 2013. *Applying Kotter's 8-Step Process for Leading Change to the Digital Transformation of an Orthopedic Surgical Practice Group in Toronto, Canada*. Journal of Health & Medical Informatics, 04(03), pp.1–4.
- Bartezzaghi, E., 2010. *L'organizzazione dell'impresa. Processi, progetti, conoscenza, persone*, Etas.
- Bartholomew, J. & Moore, B., 2014. *A guide to Becoming a dementia-friendly community*, Policy, Research and Information Department, Alzheimer's Australia NSW.
- Campbell, R.J., 2008. *Change Management in Health Care*. The Health Care Manager, 27(1), pp.23–39.

- Deming, W.E., 2000. *The New Economics: For Industry, Government, Education*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for advanced engineering study.
- Department of Health and Human Services, O.O.T.N.C.F.H.I.T., 2013. *Change Management in EHR Implementation* Health Information Technology Research Center HITRC, ed., HealthIT.gov - The National Learning Consortium (NLC).
- Ferraro, G., 2006. *The cultural dimension of international business*, Fifth edition, Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Hofstede, G., 1984. *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values*, Beverly Hills CA: SAGE Publications.
- HSE, 2008. *Improving Our Services: A Users' Guide to Managing Change in the Health Service Executive*, Organisation Development and Design Unit, HSE.
- Ishikawa, K., 1985. *What is total quality control? The Japanese way*, Prentice-Hall.
- Johnson, S., Ostaszkievicz, J. & OConnell, B., 2009. *Moving Beyond Resistance to Restraint Minimization: A Case Study of Change Management in Aged Care*. *Worldviews On Evidence-Based Nursing*, 6(4), pp.210–218.
- Kotter, J.P., 2012. *Accelerate!* *Harvard Business Review*, 90(11), pp.45–58.
- Kotter, J.P., 2014. *Accelerate: Building Strategic Agility for a Faster-Moving World*, Harvard Business Review Press.
- Kotter, J.P., 1996. *Leading Change*, Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Kotter, J.P. & Cohen, D.S., 2002. *The Heart of Change*, Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Kotter, J.P. & Schlesinger, L.A., 2008, Choosing strategies for change, *Harvard Business Review*, 86(7), pp 1-12.
- Kotter, J.P., 2007, Leading Change: Why Transformation Effort Fail, *Harvard Business Review*, 85(1), pp 1-11.
- Langley, G.J. et al., 2009. *The Improvement Guide: A Practical Approach to Enhancing Organizational Performance*, San Francisco: Wiley.
- Lewin, K., 1951, *Field Theory in Social Science*, New York, Harper and Row
- Morrison, M., 2014. *Organizational Development Theory and Practice*, CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.

Robbins, S.P., Judge, T.A., 2013, *Organizational Behaviour (15th Edition)*, New York (NY): Pearson - Chapter 18.

Sirkin, H. *et al.*, 2005, The Hard Side of Change Management, Harvard Business Review, 83(10), pp 1-10.

Shewhart, W.A., 1980. *Economic Control of Quality of Manufactured Product*, ASQ Quality Press.